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The potential negative effects of biochar on certain stages of a major fruit pest *Ceratitis capitata* (Diptera: Tephritidae)

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The use of chemical insecticides to manage insect pests is widespread, but excessive dependence on synthetic pesticides has led to pest resistance and adverse effects on the ecosystem. Therefore, there is a pressing need to employ environmentally friendly pest management techniques and optimize the usage of chemical pesticides. According to several authors, using biochar enhances the soil's ability to retain water, reduces nutrient loss, and has positive impacts against insects. This study examined the potential effects of a biochar amendment on the *Ceratitis capitata* (Wiedemann) (*C. c.*) (Diptera: Tephritidae) pupae survival and developmental outcomes to adulthood. The biochar obtained from the pyrolysis of rice husk, *Schinus terebinthifolia*, *Delonix regia*, *Leucaena leucocephala*, and the tree bark of *Leucaena leucocephala* was utilized to treat soils. Four different rates of biochar incorporation into soil (0, 25, 50, and 100% v/v) were used in the experiment. The experiment's goal was to ascertain whether adding biochar to the soil had an impact on variables including the development time of *C. c.* pupae to adult, survival of *C. c.* pupae, and adult body length and survival. In comparison to the different biochar levels and the control group, the results showed that the effect was concentration-dependent, reducing the pupae's overall survival, prolonging the time it took them to reach adulthood, and decreasing the eclosion rates of *C. c.* pupae, which dropped dramatically at the highest biochar level (100% powder), especially with tree bark of *Leucaena leucocephala*, which was more effective against development and eclosion of *C. c.* pupae. It gave the highest value of non-eclosing pupae, where the LT₅₀ value reached 22.40, days followed by rice husk (16.63 days), while the lowest value for non-eclosing was observed with *D. regia*, *L. leucocephala*, and *S. terebinthifolia*, where the LT₅₀ values were (9.58, 10.01, and 11.38 days), respectively, compared to the control group in the case of the powdered state. In the case of coarse biochar, compared to the other biochar results, the highest LT₅₀ value was observed with tree bark of *L. leucocephala* (12.67 days), followed by rice husk (10.77 days), while the lowest LT₅₀ values were obtained with *L. leucocephala*, *D. regia*, and *S. terebinthifolia* (8.03, 8.45, and 8.76 days, respectively). When comparing the biochar treatment to the control, we discovered that adult wingspan, body length, and survival were drastically reduced. According to the current study's findings, powdered biochar may be a useful tool in integrated pest management strategies for fruit fly control.

Introduction

In developing countries, owing to numerous agricultural activities, a substantial amount of waste is generated, such as animal waste and agricultural crop residues. In Egypt, the amount of waste produced each year is about 35 million tons. A significant portion of agricultural waste is used as animal feed or as a raw material for the paper industry. Due to the increasing difficulty and cost of collecting and disposing of this waste, farmers often dispose of these residues by burning them, which results in financial losses and harms human health because it increases greenhouse gas emissions. As a result of pollution and global warming on the earth's surface, climate change and its detrimental effects on the environment are anticipated. To turn these wastes into valuable goods, it is therefore imperative that they be utilized in different ways. The most crucial of these techniques is the pyrolysis process, in which biomass is converted into biochar (Masson-Delmotte *et al.*, 2021). According to Kaudal *et al.* (2016), biochar's exceptional stability allows it to retain carbon in soil for years or even millennia. It is a co-product of biomass pyrolysis, created in a high-temperature, low-oxygen environment. Up to 50% of the original carbon content of agricultural waste is preserved throughout this process (Baldock and Smernik, 2002). Biochar can be made from any organic feedstock material, such as agricultural and woody residues. Different products may be produced depending on the temperature and the biomass source used during the pyrolysis process (Lehmann and Joseph, 2009).

On the other hand, the use of chemical insecticides to manage insect pests is widespread. Chemical pesticides have a number of drawbacks despite their effectiveness. Overuse of

chemical pesticides can lead to suppression of microbial and enzymatic activities, which can degrade soil health in addition to being costly for growers. Additionally, it reduces the diversity of beneficial arthropods. In certain instances, repeated use of the same class of chemical insecticides has led to a rise in insect resistance and resurgence (Jallow *et al.*, 2017). Therefore, there is a pressing need to employ environmentally friendly pest management techniques and minimize the usage of chemical pesticides.

According to some researchers, using biochar has several benefits for environmental and agricultural objectives as well as for producers, since biochar is not harmful to the environment or human health, is comparatively less expensive, improves soil quality, reduces nutrient loss, increases soil water retention capacity, potentially reduces drought stress in surrounding vegetation, and enhances agricultural yield (Neelakanta *et al.*, 2023). Furthermore, depending on the feedstock and application rates, biochar can alter soil pH to varying degrees. The structure and solubility of nutrients in soil can be affected by pH variations, which can also affect nutrient availability. The quality and quantity of resources accessible to soil-dwelling insects can be impacted by changes in soil pH brought on by the application of biochar, which can also indirectly alter how well plants absorb nutrients, and it is one of the most significant alternatives recently employed for its positive impacts against insects. However, the impact of biochar additions on insect pests has received limited attention (Gao and DeLuca, 2022).

In addition to that, because of its unique physical characteristics, such as its large surface area, highly porous structure, carbon-rich composition, and presence of functional oxygen-

containing groups like carboxyl and hydroxyl, biochar is a promising material for managing insects in an environmentally friendly way. Insects are less likely to survive due to respiratory obstruction, cuticular abrasion, and desiccation (Wang *et al.*, 2021). Furthermore, biochar increases the availability of silicon in the soil, bolstering plant defenses through silica deposition and phytohormone-mediated biochemical reactions, including salicylic acid and jasmonic acid signaling. Together, these mechanisms increase plant resilience to diseases and herbivorous insects, demonstrating the promise of biochar as an environmentally beneficial method of integrated pest management in sustainable agriculture (Sai *et al.*, 2025).

Since, for many insects, especially during the pupation stage, soil is an essential part of their life cycle, pupal growth and development can be regulated by the type of soil, its quality, and its characteristics, including pH, depth, moisture, and temperature (Amaral *et al.*, 2021). Given that the pupal stage is thought to be the most sensitive in an insect's life cycle, intervention during pupation and eclosion can have a major impact on pest management (Singh *et al.*, 2023). Biochar is one possible soil amendment. To lessen the need for chemical pesticides and the harmful side effects of direct spraying, we investigated the potential of biochar as a pest management tool. We conducted an experiment to create direct contact during pupation by adding biochar to the pupation medium. We then monitored pupal development and adult emergence to determine whether biochar has deleterious effects on pupal and adult growth.

In Egypt, many types of fruits are grown, such as guava, mango, peach, apricot, fig, and citrus fruits, which are

among the most popular main crops. As with all agricultural crops, they are attacked by many insects, causing losses in quality and production. The Mediterranean fruit fly *Ceratitis capitata* (Wiedemann) (Diptera: Tephritidae) is a major pest of orchards. Fruit infestation by this insect pest causes both quantitative damage due to fruit loss and qualitative damage, such as reduced nutritional, aesthetic, and industrial value.

The aim of our current study is as follows:

- Create biochar by pyrolyzing the residues from (Rice husk, *Schinus terebinthifolia*, *Delonix regia*, *Leucaena leucocephala*, and the tree bark of *Leucaena leucocephala*).
- Analyze biochar using Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy to ascertain its chemical characteristics.
- Carry out laboratory tests to precisely investigate the impact of adding biochar to soil containing fruit fly pupae.
- Determine the effect of different biochar rates on the eclosion and mortality of *C. capitata* pupae and emerging adults and evaluate the effectiveness of biochar as a stand-alone treatment for pupae of *C. capitata*.

Materials and methods

1. Tested insects:

The Department of Horticultural Crop Pests, Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, provided the *C. capitata* pupae. Groups of ten pupae were placed in each plastic cup containing biochar (In two forms: powder and coarse) mixed with agricultural soil at concentrations of (0, 25, 50, and 100% v/v) under laboratory conditions (25 ± 2 °C and 65 ± 5 % RH). The surface layer (3–5 cm depth) of the soil.

2. Preparation of biochar:

Five types of biochar were prepared from four tree pruning residues, *S. terebinthifolius*, *D. regia*, *L.*

leucocephala wood, *L. leucocephala* bark and one farm waste (Rice husk), rice husk was collected from rice mill, and pruning residues were collected from trees grown in the research sector of Antoniadis Botanical Garden, Alexandria, Egypt. The tree branches were air-dried in the lab for about two months then branches were stored in the lab at room temperature for about one year. The branches were debarked and sawn into suitable size, samples were placed in crucibles, covered with a tightly fitting lid, and pyrolyzed under oxygen-limited conditions; the pyrolysis temperature was raised to 500 °C at a rate of approximately 10 °C/min in a muffle furnace and held for 60 min. Then, the biochar was allowed to cool to room temperature overnight, ground to pass through a 0.5 mm sieve and stored in sealed bags before further experiments (Hesham *et al.*, 2023).

3. Bioassays for biochar toxicity:

- The clay (Black) soil was collected from agricultural land belonging to the Agricultural Research Center.

- To prepare biochar-amended soils, the soil was thoroughly mixed with biochar in 250 mL plastic cups at four different rates: 0 (Control), 25, 50, and 100% v/v, respectively. The experiment aimed to determine whether adding biochar to soil influenced the growth, survival, and eclosion of *C. c.* pupae and emerging adults.

- Ten *C. capitata* pupae were placed in each cup, randomly assigned to the different biochar treatments, at a depth of 3-5 cm from the surface. Each treatment and control group consisted of three replicates. The survival and developmental progress of the pupae were monitored daily until adult emergence.

4. Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) analysis.

The functional groups present in the samples were detected using FTIR spectroscopy. Spectra were recorded in

the range of 400-4000 cm^{-1} , employing the Potassium bromide (KBr) pellet technique, in which 100 mg of KBr was mixed with 1 mg of sample from each agricultural biomass material (Rice husk, *S. terebinthifolia*, *D. regia*, *L. leucocephala*, and tree bark of *L. leucocephala*). The reflectance spectra were obtained by placing the sample powder directly in the infrared light path. A Perkin-Elmer FTIR spectrometer (Model Spectrum 100 Series, USA) was used to record the spectra with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} , using an average of four scans for each spectrum at a scan speed of 0.2 $\text{cm}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The functional groups of the biochar samples were determined by interpreting the spectra (Reeves, 2012 and Rajec *et al.*, 2016).

5. Data analysis:

To identify differences between soil treatments with biochar, Microsoft Excel was first used to tabulate the data. Then, a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was employed to determine whether significant differences were present among the biochar treatments. Each test was performed in triplicate, and results were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Also, every test was carried out utilizing (Costat), The Least Significant Difference (LSD) test was used to compare treatment means for significance (Snedecor and Cochran, 1989). Probit analysis of concentration–mortality data was conducted using LdPLine analytical software to estimate lethal time (LT_{50}) for each treatment concentration at a significance level of $P < 0.05$ (Finney, 1971).

Results and discussion

1. Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) analysis:

According to previous studies, the parameters of the pyrolysis process, such as temperature, pressure, heating rate, and heating time, as well as the type of biomass utilized, have a

significant impact on the yield and characteristics of the produced biochar (Gondek *et al.*, 2017). An overview of the infrared (IR) bands' peak positions and shapes, which correspond to the types of chemical bonds and the primary functional groups, was obtained from the FTIR spectra of each prepared biochar sample produced from various agricultural biomasses (Rice husk, *S. terebinthifolia*, *D. regia*, *L.*

leucocephala, and tree bark of *L. leucocephala*) at different pyrolysis temperatures. These spectra show the relationship between transmittance percentage and wavenumber (cm^{-1}), as displayed in Figure (1 a, b, c, d and e), while the corresponding functional groups identified in the biochar samples are summarized in Table (1), respectively.

(a) Rice husk sample.

(b) *Schinus terebinthifolia* sample.

(c) *Delonix regia*

(d) *Leucaena leucocephala*

(e) Tree bark of *Leucaena leucocephala*

Figure (1, a, b, c, d and e) : Fourier Transform Infrared analysis spectra of biochar samples.

Table (1): Fourier Transform Infrared bands and their corresponding functional groups observed in the spectra of rice husk, *Schinus terebinthifolia*, *Delonix regia*, *Leucaena leucocephala*, and tree bark of *Leucaena leucocephala* biochar.

Peak, cm ⁻¹	Assigned group	bands and corresponding functional groups observed in the spectrum for each biochar type				
		Rice husk	<i>Schinus terebinthifolia</i>	<i>Delonix regia</i>	<i>Leucaena leucocephala</i>	Tree bark of <i>Leucaena leucocephala</i>
400–700	Inorganic matter or -OH group	668.02	-	468.96-577.97-668.02	668.02	-
700–900	C-H aromatic stretching	-	781.78 - 876.57	781.78	-	779.25-877.04
1000–1120	C-O stretching phenolic or ester groups	1023.5	1028.2	-	1023.5	1023.7
1155–1165	C–O–C stretching aliphatic Ethers	1118.3 - 1165.7	1118.3-1165.7	1108.8	1118.3 - 1165.7	1124.8
1315–1380	Phenolic OH and aliphatic C-H	-	1317.4	1317.4-1379	1383.7	1317.1-1385.6
1410–1480	CH ₂ Alkane, C=C ring (aromatic)	1459.5	1445.3	1454.8	1459.5	-
1500–1520	benzene ring	-	-	1511.7	-	-
1600–1630	C=C stretching of aromatic components and to a smaller extent to C=O stretching in quinines and ketonic acids	1639.7	1625.4	1620.7	1635	1620.3
1700–1800	C=O/COOH gp, Ketones and carboxylic groups	1744	-	-	-	-
2800–3000	Stretching of aliphatic CH _x and alkyl structures	2853 - 2924	2853 - 2924	2853 - 2924	2853- 2924	2855.8 - 2917.7
3000–3700	-OH group, stretching of hydroxyl groups from alcohols, phenols, and organic acids	3440.7	3431.2	3431.2	3440.7	-

FTIR study results revealed that, compared to the other evaluated biochars, the *D. regia* biochar had the highest number of functional groups on its surface, including inorganic matter stretching such as silicates and carbonates, which may have caused the band peaks observed between (400–700 cm⁻¹), corresponding to the bending vibration of the C–OH carboxyl group (Fan *et al.*, 2012 and Tong *et al.*, 2013). This band appeared in all biochar samples except those from *S. terebinthifolia* and the tree bark of *L. leucocephala*. The peaks in the region between (700–900 cm⁻¹), which are characteristic of and originate from the stretching vibrations of C–H aromatic bonds (Keiluweit *et al.*, 2010 and Adeniyi *et al.*, 2019), were observed in

S. terebinthifolia, *D. regia*, and the tree bark of *L. leucocephala* samples.

According to Liu *et al.* (2010), the C–O phenolic or ester groups exhibit symmetric stretching vibrations in the (1000–1120 cm⁻¹) region. In the current study, these FTIR peaks appeared in all biochar samples except the *D. regia* sample (Feng *et al.*, 2016). It was also shown that the spectra of all the materials under investigation matched the asymmetric stretching vibrations of C–O–C aliphatic ether groups, which are responsible for the broad band intensity observed at approximately (1155–1165 cm⁻¹) (Uchimiya, 2014). Bands peaking between (1315–1380 cm⁻¹), corresponding to phenolic O–H and aliphatic C–H stretching, were detected in all biochar samples except

the rice husk sample (Wu *et al.*, 2012). Furthermore, the presence of a skeletal vibration spectrum characteristic of aromatic C=C and CH₂ alkane groups was discernible between (1410–1480 cm⁻¹) (Adeniyi *et al.*, 2020) in all biochar samples except the tree bark of *Leucaena leucocephala*.

On the other hand, a benzene ring absorption band located at (1511.7 cm⁻¹) appeared only in the *D. regia* sample. This finding is consistent with the observations of Sukiran *et al.*, 2011 and Adeniyi *et al.*, 2021, who reported that benzene ring vibrations typically appear between (1500–1520 cm⁻¹). In addition, the aromatic C=C and C=O stretching modes of conjugated ketones and quinones were in the (1600–1630 cm⁻¹) region. This confirms the presence of phenolic and carboxylic compounds in the biochar samples, particularly as pyrolysis temperature increases (Feng *et al.*, 2014 and Zhao *et al.*, 2017). They noted absorption bands corresponding to aromatic C=C stretching at 1612, 1517, and 1442 cm⁻¹. A distinct peak at (1744 cm⁻¹) was observed only in the rice husk biochar sample, which is attributed to the stretching vibrations of ketone and carboxylic (C=O/COOH) groups located within the (1700–1800 cm⁻¹) range. According to earlier studies, the carbonyl group (Eberhardt *et al.*, 2007) and ester groups in suberin (Ferreira *et al.*, 2013) are primarily represented by the C=O stretching vibration near (1735 cm⁻¹). Similarly, the absorption band at (1730 cm⁻¹), attributed to C–O stretching in carboxyl and ketone groups, was also confirmed by Sinha and Rout (2009).

The prominent and sharp absorption peaks that appeared at (2800–3000 cm⁻¹) are attributed to aliphatic groups, specifically the asymmetric and symmetric C–H methyl stretching vibrations observed in the spectra of all the studied materials. This is consistent

with the findings of Wu *et al.*, 2012; Ferreira *et al.*, 2013, and Ebadnejad *et al.*, 2018, who reported that aliphatic chains are mainly responsible for the strong peaks at 2920 and 2851 cm⁻¹, which correspond to the symmetric and asymmetric C–H stretching vibrations, respectively. Additionally, Zhao *et al.* (2013) suggested that the intensities of the peaks at 2914 and 2848 cm⁻¹ were due to the aliphatic CH₂ symmetric and asymmetric stretching vibrations, respectively. It was also observed that the O–H stretching vibrations of hydrogen-bonded hydroxyl groups were responsible for the broad and intense band appearing between (3000–3700 cm⁻¹) in all biochar samples except the tree bark of the *L. leucocephala* biochar sample. This result is in close agreement with previous studies, which reported that the stretching vibration of hydrogen-bonded O–H groups in phenolic and aliphatic compounds is represented by a band at (3300–3440 cm⁻¹) (Bourke *et al.*, 2007; Caron, 2010, and Adeniyi *et al.*, 2021). These findings are consistent with the observations of Chen *et al.*, 2011 and Kan *et al.*, 2016, who stated that several processes, such as aromatization, isomerization, dehydration, and charring, occur simultaneously and sequentially during the biomass carbonization/pyrolysis process.

2. Impact of biochar on eclosion duration:

Applying biochar has produced significant effects in reducing soil-dwelling insect populations. Its physicochemical properties, high surface area, and porous structure are important factors that influence insect populations and modify soil conditions. Insect behavior, development, reproduction, and survival rates have all been affected by the insecticidal properties of biochar amendments

(Rice, 2022). The period between pupal placement in treatments and complete adult emergence was defined as the eclosion duration. Furthermore, the pupae exhibited deformities that extended into the adult stage (Figure 2 a and b) in the treated groups. When

(a) Pupae in control group.

Figure (2): Pupae of *Ceratitidis capitata*

Groups of pupae, each consisting of 10 pupae of *C. capitata* (C.c.), were used to evaluate the insecticidal activity of the different biochar types applied at concentrations of 0, 25, 50, and 100% (v/v) with agricultural soil. The effects of the biochar types on the developmental duration from pupae to adult stage, as well as any morphological changes in the emerging adults, were monitored. The results presented in Tables (2 and 3), for both powder and coarse biochar forms, demonstrated that the application of biochar had noticeable adverse effects on pupae that were in direct contact with the biochar-treated soil under laboratory conditions. The developmental period from pupae to adults was significantly influenced by biochar treatments, as described below. According to our findings, compared with the lower biochar concentrations and the control (0% biochar), the biochar treatments caused a reduction in pupae-to-adult, survival and delayed pupal development. The eclosion duration was significantly longer at the highest

compared to the control group, treated pupae required significantly more time to eclose. The Ldp line statistical analysis was used to determine the median lethal time (LT₅₀), with a significance level of (P < 0.05).

(b) Pupae in treated group.

biochar application level (100%). Also, the pupal eclosion rate decreased markedly at the 100% biochar level, especially with powder form.

The longest eclosion period was recorded for the tree bark of *L. leucocephala*, where the LT₅₀ value reached (22.40 days), followed by rice husk (16.63 days) and *S. terebinthifolia* (11.38 days), respectively. However, *L. leucocephala* wood biochar and *D. regia* showed the least effect on pupal eclosion, with LT₅₀ values of 10.01 and 9.58 days, respectively. In the coarse biochar form, as shown in Table (3), the longest eclosion period was also observed for the tree bark of *L. leucocephala*, with an LT₅₀ value of 12.67 days, followed by rice husk (10.77 days). Meanwhile, there were no significant differences among *S. terebinthifolia*, *D. regia*, and *L. leucocephala* biochar, which showed the weakest effects on pupal eclosion with LT₅₀ values of 8.76, 8.45, and 8.03 days, respectively.

Table (2): Estimated lethal time (LT₅₀) values for *Ceratitis capitata* pupae exposed to different types of biochar powder at various concentrations (25%, 50%, and 100%).

Biochar	Conc	LT ₅₀ Day	Confidence limits		Slope	X ²
			Lower	Upper		
Rice husk	25%	9.40	9.19	9.64	16.15±1.65	1.51
	50%	12.22	11.84	12.81	14.70±1.97	0.43
	100%	16.63	34.05	46.20	10.67±4.04	0.07
<i>Schinus terebinthifolia</i>	25%	7.62	7.41	7.85	11.37±1.14	1.64
	50%	8.74	8.47	9.07	9.18±0.89	1.71
	100%	11.38	11.07	11.79	11.87±1.23	1.64
<i>Delonix regia</i>	25%	7.32	7.16	7.50	17.03±1.84	0.66
	50%	9.50	8.68	10.90	10.05±0.97	7.76
	100%	9.58	9.29	9.92	8.97±0.78	2.66
<i>Leucaena leucocephala</i>	25%	7.55	6.87	7.98	5.55±1.13	5.58
	50%	8.86	8.19	10.17	10.19±0.95	8.56
	100%	10.01	9.66	10.46	8.25±0.76	1.10
Tree bark of <i>Leucaena leucocephala</i>	25%	9.13	8.80	9.68	12.84±2.04	0.002
	50%	10.82	10.17	12.11	8.48±1.42	0.34
	100%	22.40	-	-	6,66±4.38	0.43

Table (3): Estimated lethal time (LT₅₀) values for *Ceratitis capitata* pupae exposed to different types of coarse biochar at various concentrations (25%, 50%, and 100%).

Biochar	Conc	LT ₅₀ Day	Confidence limits		Slope	X ²
			Lower	Upper		
Rice husk	25%	7.27	-	-	8.98±1.06	7.88
	50%	9.58	8.91	10.62	10.50±0.99	6.69
	100%	10.77	10.22	11.66	6.51±0.93	0.71
<i>Schinus terebinthifolia</i>	25%	6.89	6.67	7.09	11.38±1.15	3.79
	50%	6.96	6.79	7.13	15.23±1.68	0.17
	100%	8.76	8.55	8.98	13.55±1.33	1.02
<i>Delonix regia</i>	25%	7.11	6.96	7.27	17.93±1.82	0.30
	50%	7.43	-	-	13.64±1.22	7.90
	100%	8.45	8.25	8.67	12.47±1.02	4.09
<i>Leucaena leucocephala</i>	25%	6.52	6.31	6.70	13.46±1.65	0.81
	50%	7.27	7.03	7.50	9.80±1.08	5.36
	100%	8.03	-	-	13.80±1.32	6.28
Tree bark of <i>Leucaena leucocephala</i>	25%	7.27	7.06	7.49	10.67±1.11	2.85
	50%	8.22	7.93	8.59	9.11±1.11	0.18
	100%	12.67	11.45	16.54	5.68±1.40	0.07

A similar finding to ours was also reported by Cook and Neto (2018), who showed that insect species exposed to dry biochar material experienced adverse effects, with a reduction in survival rates for both small (<150 µm) and coarse (>1.0 mm) particle sizes. Insects exposed to, and perhaps consuming, biochar may respond differently depending on its moisture content and particle size. As for the mean eclosion rate of the pupae, the results were as shown in the following tables. After being directly exposed to biochar in the medium, pupae treated with biochar showed significantly lower eclosion rates than those in the control group, especially at higher concentrations. The highest concentration (100%) biochar treatment resulted in the longest eclosion time compared to all other treatments and the control.

At a 25% concentration, as shown in Table (4), the sequence of effects from most to least influential was as follows: the lowest mean number of eclosed pupae occurred in the group treated with the tree bark of *L. leucocephala* (3.76 pupae), with the average highest eclosion occurring on the 9th day. This was followed by rice

husk (4.57 pupae; 10th day), and then by *L. leucocephala*, *D. regia*, and *S. terebinthifolia* (6.43, 6.85, and 6.91 pupae, respectively), where the average highest eclosion occurred on the 9th day, except for *D. regia*, where it occurred on the 8th day. At the 50% concentration (Table 5), the rice husk biochar treatment showed the strongest effect. The mean eclosion rate of pupae was (1.86 pupae), with the highest eclosion occurring on the 12th day, followed by tree bark of *Leucaena leucocephala* (3.00 pupae; 10th day), *D. regia* (4.86 pupae; 11th day), *L. leucocephala* (5.19 pupae; 10th day), and *S. terebinthifolia* (5.43 pupae; 10th day). The most effective concentration, as shown in Table (6), was 100%, particularly for the tree bark of *L. leucocephala*, where the mean eclosion rate of pupae was (0.14 pupae) emerging after 13 days. This was followed by rice husk (0.33 pupae; 13 days), *S. terebinthifolia* (2.86 pupae; 12 days), *L. leucocephala* (4.29 pupae; 11 days), and *D. regia* (4.81 pupae; 11 days). The emerged adult insects appeared extremely weak and died within 4-8 hrs.

Table (4): Fruit fly pupal eclosion rate after treatment with different types of powdered biochar at 25% concentration.

Compounds	Conc. (%)	Mean number of eclosing pupae / days ± SD							GM
		7 days	8 days	9 days	10 days	11days	12 days	13 days	
Rice husk	25	0.33±0.47 ^c	1±1.41 ^b	4±2.83 ^b	6.67±1.70 ^{ab}	6.67±1.70 ^{ab}	6.67±1.70 ^{ab}	6.67±1.70 ^{ab}	4.57
<i>Schinus terebinthifolia</i>	25	3.67±1.25 ^b	6.33±1.25 ^a	7.67±1.70 ^{ab}	6.91				
<i>Delonix regia</i>	25	4±1.63 ^{ab}	7.33±1.25 ^a	7.33±1.25 ^{ab}	6.85				
<i>Leucaena leucocephala</i>	25	3.67±1.70 ^b	6.33±2.63 ^a	7±2.16 ^{ab}	6.43				
Tree bark of <i>Leucaena leucocephala</i>	25	0.67±0.47 ^c	2.33±1.25 ^b	4.67±1.25 ^b	4.67±1.25 ^b	4.67±1.25 ^b	4.67±1.25 ^b	4.67±1.25 ^b	3.76
Control	-	6.33±0.47 ^a	8.67±0.47 ^a	8.67±0.47 ^a	8.67±0.47 ^a	8.67±0.47 ^a	8.67±0.47 ^a	8.67±0.47 ^a	8.34
LSD (0.05)	25	2.481	3.302	3.866	3.302	3.302	3.302	3.302	3.265

Means followed by the different letters in column are significantly different according to the L.S.D. test at (p < 0.05) probability level.

Table (5): Fruit fly pupal eclosion rate after treatment with different types of powdered biochar at 50% concentration.

Compounds	Conc. (%)	Mean number of eclosing pupae / days ± SD							GM
		7 days	8 days	9 days	10 days	11days	12 days	13 days	
Rice husk	50	0±0 ^c	0±0 ^d	0.33±0.47 ^d	1±0.82 ^c	2.33±0.94 ^c	4.67±1.70 ^b	4.67±1.70 ^b	1.86
<i>Schinus terebinthifolia</i>	50	1.67±1.63 ^b	4±1.63 ^b	5.67±2.06 ^b	6.67±1.70 ^{ab}	6.67±1.70 ^{ab}	6.67±1.70 ^{ab}	6.67±1.70 ^{ab}	5.43
<i>Delonix regia</i>	50	0.33±1.70 ^{bc}	2.67±1.70 ^{bc}	5±0.82 ^{bc}	6±1.63 ^{ab}	6.67±0.94 ^{ab}	6.67±0.94 ^{ab}	6.67±0.94 ^{ab}	4.86
<i>Leucaena leucocephala</i>	50	1±1.70 ^{bc}	4.33±1.70 ^{bc}	5.67±2.06 ^b	6.33±2.06 ^{ab}	6.33±2.06 ^{ab}	6.33±2.06 ^{ab}	6.33±2.06 ^{ab}	5.19
Tree bark of <i>Leucaena leucocephala</i>	50	1.33±0.47 ^{bc}	1.33±0.47 ^{cd}	2.33±0.47 ^{cd}	4±0.82 ^b	4±0.82 ^{bc}	4±0.82 ^b	4±0.82 ^b	3
Control	-	6.33±0.47 ^a	8.67±0.47 ^a	8.67±0.47 ^a	8.67±0.47 ^a	8.67±0.47 ^a	8.67±0.47 ^a	8.67±0.47 ^a	8.34
LSD (0.05)	50	1.511	2.652	2.781	2.995	2.781	3.053	3.053	2.689

Means followed by the different letters in column are significantly different according to the L.S.D. test at (p < 0.05) probability level.

Table (6): Fruit fly pupal eclosion rate after treatment with different types of powdered biochar at 100% concentration.

Compounds	Conc. (%)	Mean number of eclosing pupae / days ± SD							GM
		7 days	8 days	9 days	10 days	11days	12 days	13 days	
Rice husk	100	0±0 ^b	0±0 ^d	0±0 ^c	0±0 ^d	0.33±0.47 ^d	0.67 ±0.94 ^c	1.33 ±1.25 ^c	0.33
<i>Schinus terebinthifolia</i>	100	0±0 ^b	0.33±0.47 ^{cd}	1±0 ^c	2.67±0.47 ^c	4.67±0.47 ^c	5.67 ±1.70 ^b	5.67 ±1.70 ^b	2.86
<i>Delonix regia</i>	100	1±0.82 ^b	2.33±2.06 ^b	4.67±0.94 ^b	5.67±1.70 ^b	6.67±0.94 ^b	6.67 ±0.94 ^{ab}	6.67 ±0.94 ^{ab}	4.81
<i>Leucaena leucocephala</i>	100	1±0.82 ^b	2±0 ^{bc}	3.67±0.94 ^b	5.33±1.25 ^b	6±1.63 ^{bc}	6 ±1.63 ^b	6 ±1.63 ^{ab}	4.29
Tree bark of <i>Leucaena leucocephala</i>	100	0±0 ^b	0±0 ^d	0±0 ^c	0±0 ^d	0±0 ^d	0.33 ±0.47 ^c	0.67 ±0.94 ^c	0.14
Control	-	6.33±0.47 ^a	8.67±0.47 ^a	8.67±0.47 ^a	8.67±0.47 ^a	8.67±0.47 ^a	8.67±0.47 ^a	8.67±0.47 ^a	8.34
LSD (0.05)	100	1.109	1.922	1.258	1.967	1.828	2.481	2.685	1.893

Means followed by the different letters in column are significantly different according to the L.S.D. test at (p < 0.05) probability level.

On the other hand, in the coarse biochar state, the results, as explained in Table (7), showed that the biochar of the tested types was less effective than that tested in the powdered state, as the duration of pupal eclosion did not differ significantly at a concentration of 25% compared with the control group. The mean results were arranged from the strongest effect to the weakest as follows: rice husk (7 pupae), tree bark of *L. leucocephala* (7.38 pupae), *D. regia* (7.76 pupae), *S. terebinthifolia* (8.19 pupae), and *L. leucocephala* (8.62 pupae), where the average highest number of eclosed pupae occurred on the 9th day for the first two and the 8th day for the remaining three, respectively. As for the 50% concentration test (Table 8), the biochar that had the strongest influence on the duration of pupal eclosion was rice husk (4.76 pupae), where the average highest number of eclosed pupae was observed on the 11th day, followed by tree bark of *L. leucocephala* (5.57 pupae), *L. leucocephala* (7.19 pupae), *D. regia* (7.38 pupae), and *S. terebinthifolia* (7.85 pupae), where the average highest number of eclosed pupae for the tree bark of *L. leucocephala*, *L. leucocephala* and *D. regia* treatments occurred on the 9th day but *S. terebinthifolia* was at 8th, respectively. Moreover, for the 100% concentration

test (Table 9), the biochar that caused the longest duration of pupal eclosion was tree bark of *Leucaena leucocephala* (2.43 pupae), where the average highest number of eclosed pupae was recorded on the 11th day, followed by rice husk (3.67 pupae, 11th day too), *S. terebinthifolia* (5.76 pupae), *D. regia* (6.14 pupae, 10th day), and *L. leucocephala* (6.24 pupae, 9th day), respectively.

3. Impact of biochar on adult survival duration:

Treatment with all types of biochar had a considerable impact on the adult survival duration. Biochar treatment significantly reduced the survival time of adults. Compared to adults from the untreated control group, the time to mortality decreased with each increase in biochar concentration in the soil. The adults that emerged from the pupae were in a state of severe fatigue and died within 4-8 hrs. after exposure to 50% and 100% powdered biochar, as shown in Figure (3 a and b) and Table (10). The same observation was also recorded for adults treated with 25% powdered rice husk biochar. As for the groups treated with coarse biochar, the emerging adult insects died within 12–24 hrs. in the group treated with rice husk at concentrations of 50% and 100%, as well as in the group treated with 100% tree bark of *L. leucocephala*.

Table (7): Fruit fly pupal eclosion rate after treatment with different types of coarse biochar at 25% concentration.

Compounds	Conc. (%)	Mean number of eclosing pupae / days ± SD							GM
		7 days	8 days	9 days	10 days	11days	12 days	13 days	
Rice husk	25	5.33±1.25 ^a	7±1.63 ^a	7.33±1.25 ^a	7.33±1.25 ^a	7.33±1.25 ^a	7.33±1.25 ^a	7.33±1.25 ^a	7
<i>Schinus terebinthifolia</i>	25	5.33±1.70 ^a	8.67±1.89 ^a	8.67±1.89 ^a	8.67±1.89 ^a	8.67±1.89 ^a	8.67±1.89 ^a	8.67±1.89 ^a	8.19
<i>Delonix Regia</i>	25	4.33±2.63 ^a	8.33±1.70 ^a	8.33±1.70 ^a	8.33±1.70 ^a	8.33±1.70 ^a	8.33±1.70 ^a	8.33±1.70 ^a	7.76
<i>Leucaena leucocephala</i>	25	6.33±0.47 ^a	9±1.40 ^a	9±1.41 ^a	8.62				
Tree bark of <i>Leucaena leucocephala</i>	25	4.33±1.25 ^a	7.33±1.70 ^a	8±2.16 ^a	8±2.16 ^a	8±2.16 ^a	8±2.16 ^a	8±2.16 ^a	7.38
Control	-	6.33±0.47 ^a	8.67±0.47 ^a	8.67±0.47 ^a	8.67±0.47 ^a	8.67±0.47 ^a	8.67±0.47 ^a	8.67±0.47 ^a	8.34
LSD (0.05)	25	3.248	3.355	3.432	3.432	3.432	3.432	3.432	3.395

Means followed by the different letters in column are significantly different according to the L.S.D. test at (p < 0.05) probability level.

Table (8): Fruit fly pupal eclosion rate after treatment with different types of coarse biochar at 50% concentration.

Compounds	Conc. (%)	Mean number of eclosing pupae / days ± SD							GM
		7 days	8 days	9 days	10 days	11days	12 days	13 days	
Rice husk	50	0.33±0.47 ^c	2.33±1.25 ^c	4.67±0.47 ^b	6±0.82 ^b	6.67±0.47 ^a	6.67±0.47 ^a	6.67±0.47 ^a	4.76
<i>Schinus terebinthifolia</i>	50	5±0.82 ^{ab}	8.33±0.47 ^a	8.33±0.47 ^a	8.33±0.47 ^{ab}	8.33±0.47 ^a	8.33±0.47 ^a	8.33±0.47 ^a	7.85
<i>Delonix regia</i>	50	4±0 ^{ab}	7.67±1.25 ^a	8±1.63 ^a	8±1.63 ^{ab}	8±1.63 ^a	8±1.63 ^a	8±1.63 ^a	7.38
<i>Leucaena leucocephala</i>	50	5±2.16 ^{ab}	7±1.41 ^{ab}	7.67±1.70 ^a	7.67±1.70 ^{ab}	7.67±1.70 ^a	7.67±1.70 ^a	7.67±1.70 ^a	7.19
Tree bark of <i>Leucaena leucocephala</i>	50	2.67±2.06 ^{bc}	4.67±1.25 ^{bc}	6.33±1.25 ^{ab}	6.33±1.25 ^{ab}	6.33±1.25 ^a	6.33±1.25 ^a	6.33±1.25 ^a	5.57
Control	-	6.33±0.47 ^a	8.67±0.47 ^a	8.67±0.47 ^a	8.67±0.47 ^a	8.67±0.47 ^a	8.67±0.47 ^a	8.67±0.47 ^a	8.34
LSD (0.05)	50	2.813	2.372	2.481	2.551	2.481	2.481	2.481	2.523

Means followed by the different letters in column are significantly different according to the L.S.D. test at (p < 0.05) probability level.

Table (9): Fruit fly pupal eclosion rate treated with different types of coarse biochar at 100% conc.

Compounds	Conc. (%)	Mean number of eclosing pupae / days ± SD							GM
		7 days	8 days	9 days	10 days	11days	12 days	13 days	
Rice husk	100	1±0 ^{bc}	2±0.82 ^{cd}	3.33±0.94 ^c	4.33±1.70 ^b	5±1.63 ^{bc}	5±1.63 ^{bc}	5±1.63 ^{bc}	3.67
<i>Schinus terebinthifolia</i>	100	1±0.82 ^{bc}	2.67±1.25 ^{cd}	6±1.63 ^b	7.67±1.70 ^a	7.67±1.70 ^{ab}	7.67±1.70 ^{ab}	7.67±1.70 ^{ab}	5.76
<i>Delonix regia</i>	100	1.33±0.47 ^b	4±1.41 ^{bc}	7±0.82 ^{ab}	7.67±1.25 ^a	7.67±1.25 ^{ab}	7.67±1.25 ^{ab}	7.67±1.25 ^{ab}	6.14
<i>Leucaena leucocephala</i>	100	1.33±0.94 ^b	5.67±2.06 ^b	7.33±1.25 ^{ab}	7.33±1.25 ^a	7.33±1.25 ^{ab}	7.33±1.25 ^{ab}	7.33±1.25 ^{ab}	6.24
Tree bark of <i>Leucaena leucocephala</i>	100	0±0 ^c	1.33±0.47 ^d	2±0.82 ^c	2.67±0.47 ^b	3.67±1.25 ^c	3.67±1.25 ^c	3.67±1.25 ^c	2.43
Control	-	6.33±0.47 ^a	8.67±0.47 ^a	8.67±0.47 ^a	8.67±0.47 ^a	8.67±0.47 ^a	8.67±0.47 ^a	8.67±0.47 ^a	8.34
LSD (0.05)	100	1.258	2.652	2.297	2.718	2.875	2.875	2.875	2.507

Means followed by the different letters in column are significantly different according to the L.S.D. test at (p < 0.05) probability level.

(a) Emerging adult in control group

(b) Emerging adult in treated group

Figure (3): Emerging adult of *Ceratitis capitata*.

Table (10): Emerging adults of *Ceratitis capitata* for pupae exposed to some types of biochar at different concentrations (25%, 50% and 100%).

Compounds	Conc. (%)	Emerging Adults of <i>Ceratitis capitata</i>	
		Powder	Coarse
Rice husk	25	Death	Lived
	50	Death	Death
	100	Death	Death
<i>Schinus terebinthifolia</i>	25	Lived	Lived
	50	Death	Lived
	100	Death	Lived
<i>Delonix regia</i>	25	Lived	Lived
	50	Death	Lived
	100	Death	Lived
<i>Leucaena leucocephala</i>	25	Lived	Lived
	50	Death	Lived
	100	Death	Lived
Tree bark of <i>Leucaena leucocephala</i>	25	Death	Lived
	50	Death	Lived
	100	Death	Death
Control	-	Lived	Lived

4.

Biochar's impact on adult body length:

The results in Table (11) showed that a significant difference in the mean adult body length between the treatment groups and the control group appeared only at the highest concentration (100%) of biochar for both powdered and coarse states. The mean body length of emerging adults decreased after the pupae were treated with biochar. There was no significant difference in the length of adult insects between the other treated groups (25% and 50% biochar). The greatest reduction in average adult length was observed in the group treated with rice husk biochar, where the mean length was (3.97 mm), while

the least effect was recorded in the group treated with *L. leucocephala* biochar, with a mean length of (5.17 mm) in the powdered state. In the coarse biochar state, the results also showed that the most affected group was rice husk biochar, with a mean length of (4.6 mm), while the least affected group was *S. terebinthifolia*, with a mean length of (5.5 mm). Also, there was no significant difference in the mean adult length between the groups treated with the lower biochar concentrations (25% and 50%) and the control group.

Table (11): Effect of various biochar treatments on length of adults at concentration 100%.

Compounds	Mean length of adult's mm \pm SD	
	Powder	Coarse
Control	7.33 \pm 0.47 ^a	7.33 \pm 0.47 ^a
Rice husk	3.97 \pm 0.29 ^b	4.6 \pm 0.47 ^{cd}
<i>Schinus terebinthifolia</i>	4.5 \pm 0.41 ^b	5.5 \pm 0.41 ^{bc}
<i>Delonix regia</i>	4.43 \pm 0.41 ^b	4.9 \pm 0.47 ^d
<i>Leucaena leucocephala</i>	5.17 \pm 0.47 ^b	5.33 \pm 0.62 ^b
Tree bark of <i>Leucaena leucocephala</i>	4.5 \pm 0.94 ^b	5.43 \pm 0.41 ^{bc}
LSD (0.05)	1.178	1.048

Means followed by the different letters in column are significantly different according to the L.S.D. test at ($p < 0.05$) probability level.

Our findings were consistent with several studies that have documented the insecticidal properties of biochar against various insect species. This agrees with the observations of Cook and Neto (2018), who found that three of the four insect species studied exhibited a substantial decrease in adult survival upon direct contact with dry biochar. Significantly lower survival rates were recorded for *Ips pini* (Coleoptera: Curculionidae: Scolytinae), *Temnochila chlorodia* (Coleoptera: Trogossitidae), and *Formica obscuripes* (Hymenoptera: Formicidae), while *Enoclerus sphegeus* (Coleoptera: Curculionidae: Scolytinae) was unaffected.

Other researchers have also observed declines in the number of specific mite or beetle species. Biochar-induced changes in soil physicochemical characteristics, such as pH, nutrient availability, and microbial activity, can contribute to shifts in the relative abundance of soil-dwelling insects. These changes may affect the competitive advantage of certain insect groups, thereby influencing their population size, feeding behavior, growth, and reproduction within the soil ecosystem (Paz-Ferreiro *et al.*, 2016, and Wahba *et al.*, 2022).

Additionally, Hassan *et al.* (2022) assessed the effectiveness of four distinct forms of biochar against various stored-product insects and reported that biochar produced from chicken manure was the most effective. The most affected species were *Rhyzopertha dominica* and *Oryzaephilus surinamensis*. They also found that insect mortality increased as biochar particle size decreased. Similarly, Elad *et al.* (2010) demonstrated that biochar treatment reduced the likelihood of

infestation by the broad mite (*Polyphagotarsonemus latus* Banks) in pepper and tomato plants.

Abit *et al.* (2012) added that the physical structure and water-retention capacity of biochar make it potentially abrasive to an insect's cuticle, thereby increasing the risk of dehydration. They observed that smaller particles had a more significant impact on the longevity and survival of ants, with mortality rates rising alongside biochar concentration. Biochar can decompose into finer particles upon contact, which may enter an insect's spiracles and interfere with respiration (Neelakanta *et al.*, 2023).

The results of the present study are also consistent with previous research indicating that biochar can impair the development and reproduction of certain sap-sucking herbivorous insects. For instance, laboratory experiments have shown that biochar-amended soils can reduce developmental performance and fecundity in the plant hopper *Nilaparvata lugens* (Hou *et al.*, 2017) and *Laodelphax striatellus* on rice (Fu *et al.*, 2018), as well as in the English grain aphid *Sitobion avenae* on wheat (Chen *et al.*, 2020). Similarly, biochar treatment was found to reduce damage caused by the broad mite *P. latus* on pepper (Elad *et al.*, 2011). Furthermore, applying biochar has been shown to delay nymphal development and reduce adult fertility in the brown planthopper *N. lugens* (Hou *et al.*, 2015) and inhibit growth and development of the white-backed planthopper *Sogatella furcifera* (Waqas *et al.*, 2018).

Moreover, biochar has also been reported to affect soil macrofauna such as earthworms. For example, the density of

cocoons and juveniles of *Pontoscolex corethrurus* decreased following biochar application (Topoliantz *et al.*, 2005). Similarly, Schmidt *et al.* (1999) observed that earthworms in biochar soil mixtures died within seven days of incubation. These authors attributed the mortality to biochar particles adhering to the worms' bodies and causing serious physical damage. A reduction in feeding activity, possibly to avoid ingesting biochar particles, may also explain the commonly observed weight loss among earthworms (Hale *et al.*, 2013). Other frequently reported negative effects of biochar on earthworms include delayed growth and reduced reproductive rates (Elliston and Oliver, 2020). Because biochar is porous, it can absorb and retain moisture, which may lead to insect desiccation (Abit *et al.*, 2012). Furthermore, Viger *et al.* (2015) noted that the rough texture of biochar particles can abrade the insect cuticle, increase water loss, and cause dehydration. Fine biochar particles may also enter the insect's spiracles, obstructing respiration and oxygen intake, potentially leading to suffocation (Spokas *et al.*, 2009).

There is increasing interest in using biochar as a sustainable tool to reduce insect pests. The impact of biochar varies depending on the feedstock used and the soil conditions in which it is applied. According to the present study, biochar interferes with the insect life cycle, exhibiting insecticidal activity and exerting negative effects on pupal development, eclosion success, survival, and adult emergence, particularly at higher concentrations. Our results showed that applying 100% biochar, especially that derived from rice husk and tree bark of *L. leucocephala*, to the soil significantly inhibited the development of *C. capitata* pupae and prolonged the eclosion period. Furthermore, the emerging adults exhibited severe deformities, reduced body length, and rapid mortality. These adverse effects may be attributed to the chemical composition of the biochar, particularly their high content of phenolic compounds, carboxylic acids, and other organic substances, which may contribute to their insecticidal activity. Therefore, biochar applications could provide an additional

benefit by suppressing fruit fly pest populations. Through direct interaction, biochar represents an innovative and eco-friendly approach to insect management. Its physical properties, such as abrasiveness, porosity, and hygroscopicity, can cause cuticular damage, respiratory blockage, and dehydration in insects. Such injuries during the pupal and adult stages may impair reproductive capacity, thereby reducing the likelihood of future crop infestations.

Overall, these findings demonstrate that biochar is not only an effective soil amendment but also holds great promise as a sustainable pest management tool. Its use could decrease reliance on chemical insecticides, mitigate associated environmental risks, enhance soil health, promote biodiversity, and improve agricultural productivity. However, before biochar can be fully integrated into agricultural and integrated pest management (IPM) programs, its environmental safety and potential effects on beneficial organisms must be carefully evaluated.

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